

INFLUENCE OF URBAN RECREATION AND INFRASTRUCTURAL RESOURCES ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURIST DESTINATIONS

Irina Solomina*, Dmitry Tsapuk**, Olga Isaeva***, Irina Shadskaja**** & Ivan Kapustin*****

Abstract

The article is devoted to the consideration of socio-economic aspects of the development of urban tourist destinations. A city as a tourist destination is a settlement that possesses a sufficient number of tourist and recreational resources, social infrastructure facilities, at least one type of transport accessibility, positioning itself as a tourist center within the state to which it belongs. Measures for the development of the tourist and recreational sector in tourist cities should provide for a comprehensive solution to the priority problems of the urban development and main tourist zones of cities, further strengthening tourist, excursion, and sanatorium-resort services, expanding the range of recreational and tourist services and creating an appropriate material, technical and personnel base, increasing the volume of income from all type tourist activities in contemporary conditions.

Keywords: Tourism; Destination; City; Economy; Resources.

ASPECTOS SÓCIO-ECONÔMICOS DO DESENVOLVIMENTO DOS DESTINOS TURÍSTICOS URBANOS

Resumo

O artigo é dedicado à consideração dos aspectos socioeconômicos do desenvolvimento dos destinos turísticos urbanos. Uma cidade como destino turístico é um povoado que possui um número suficiente de recursos turísticos e recreativos, instalações de infra-estruturas sociais, pelo menos um tipo de acessibilidade de transportes, posicionando-se como centro turístico dentro do estado a que pertence. As medidas para o desenvolvimento do setor turístico e recreativo nas cidades turísticas devem proporcionar uma solução global para os problemas prioritários do desenvolvimento urbano e das principais zonas turísticas das cidades, reforçar ainda mais os serviços turísticos, de excursões e de sanatórios-resorts, expandir a gama de serviços recreativos e turísticos e criar uma base material, técnica e pessoal adequada, aumentando o volume de rendimentos de todo o tipo de atividades turísticas em condições contemporâneas.

Palavras-chave: Turismo; Destino; Cidade; Economia; Recursos.

ASPECTOS SOCIOECONÓMICOS DEL DESARROLLO DE LOS DESTINOS TURÍSTICOS URBANOS

Resumen

El artículo está dedicado a la consideración de los aspectos socioeconómicos del desarrollo de los destinos turísticos urbanos. Una ciudad como destino turístico es un asentamiento que posee un número suficiente de recursos turísticos y recreativos, instalaciones de infraestructura social, al menos un tipo de accesibilidad de transporte, posicionándose como un centro turístico dentro del estado al que pertenece. Las medidas para el desarrollo del sector turístico y recreativo en las ciudades turísticas deben prever una solución integral de los problemas prioritarios del desarrollo urbano y de las principales zonas turísticas de las ciudades, reforzando aún más los servicios turísticos, de excursión y de sanatorio-balneario, ampliando la gama de servicios recreativos y turísticos y creando una base material, técnica y de personal adecuada, aumentando el volumen de ingresos de todo tipo de actividades turísticas en las condiciones contemporáneas.

Palabras clave: Turismo; Destino; Ciudad; Economía; Recursos.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the era of mobility and increased speed of movement, tourism is becoming increasingly developed. Tourism is stimulated by the national economies of the countries where it is one of the leading branches of the economy and is carried out by tourists who seek to broaden their horizons, get acquainted with other cultures and peoples, actively relax, recover, have fun, or simply follow modern fashion trends (Choi et al., 2022).

Currently, tourism remains one of the constantly dynamically developing economic sectors with high potential and significant prospects. It would seem that tourism has a spontaneous character; however, in fact, it is characterized by certain directions of tourist flows, which form tourist regions and centers (Lee & Li, 2019).

In this context, tourist centers represent local territories that enjoy special attention and popularity among tourists and concentrate a significant tourist and recreational potential (Ksenofontova et al., 2021). This applies to urban settlements, including megacities,

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whose functions are not only of exceptional national, regional but often of planetary importance.

Besides, in the context of rapid urbanized processes and the growing role of cities in the life of society, it is important to preserve and increase the tourist and recreational potential, which requires significant research in this area (Santangelo et al., 2018). Cities remain a special form of social organization. People live, work, and have a rest in cities.

A single city is a tourist destination for those people who do not live in it. The city is one of the most difficult centers of human life (Yang et al., 2022). It represents an arena of political, economic, and social processes taking place in the modern world, a place of concentration of important values obtained by human labor.

Cities are complex systems that include territory, population, production, natural and labor resources, and infrastructure (Samadi Parviznejad & Akhavan, 2021). They should exist in harmonious interaction and complement each other.

At the same time, the city, as a tourist destination, is a settlement that has a sufficient number of tourist and recreational resources, institutions of social infrastructure, at least one of the types of transport accessibility (airports, railway stations, bus stations, highways) positioning itself as a tourist center within the state.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

The study of issues related to the development of tourism has found reflection in the works of Adashova (2019), Vishnevskaya (2020), Evsyukov (2019), Koroleva (2019), Molchanova (2020), Petrenko (2020), and others.

Adashova and Rogoten (2019) understand an urban tourist destination as an urban area that has a certain attraction for tourists. Vishnevskaya (2020) notes that urban tourist destinations are places in cities, visiting which leaves tourists with a variety of impressions, experiences, and emotions.

Evsyukov and Gomilevskaya (2019) give the following definition of an urban tourist destination: it is a physical space within the city where the visitor spends time. It contains tourism products, such as services and attractions, and tourism resources. This space has physical and administrative boundaries that determine the way it is managed, as well as objects and perceptions that determine its market competitiveness.

Koroleva (2019) defines an urban tourist destination as a territory that offers a certain set of services that meet the needs of tourists and satisfy their demand for transportation, overnight stay, food, and entertainment. The researcher also distinguishes the so-called primary urban destination, which is the main

purpose of the trip, and the secondary urban destination.

There are two approaches to the definition of an urban tourist destination: geographical and client-oriented. According to the first approach, an urban tourist destination is an urban area with certain tourist resources (Molchanova, 2020).

The client-oriented approach considers that this urban area should still have a certain attractiveness for tourists (Petrenko, 2020).

We adhere to a client-oriented approach, according to which an urban tourist destination is an urban area that is attractive to tourists and has the necessary infrastructure to provide accommodation, food, transport services, entertainment, attractions, and information and communications systems.

However, despite significant scientific research on this problem, factors that influence the choice of a tourist destination based on ratings, as well as urban development activities to increase excursion attractiveness, require an in-depth study.

3 METHODS

The study was conducted in 2021-2022 in the following universities: Russian State University of Tourism and Service, Moscow Polytechnic University, Russian State Social University, and Russian State University of Transport.

The theoretical and methodological basis of the research includes an abstract-logical method, methods of induction, deduction, analysis, synthesis, and systematization, used to substantiate approaches to the development of urban tourist destinations.

The selection of sources was carried out considering the socio-economic aspects of the development of urban tourist destinations. We used statistical data of state bodies, legislative and regulatory documents governing the urban tourist destinations functioning, as well as the results of conducted scientific research (Agamirova et al., 2017; Markova et al., 2021; Solomina, 2016).

The main research method was the method of ranking capital cities, which included the formation of a rating based on internal and external factors of tourism development in European capitals. The rating included 37 European capitals: Paris, London, Rome, Berlin, Moscow, Madrid, Amsterdam, Athens, Vienna, Prague, Budapest, Stockholm, Helsinki, Brussels, Warsaw, Copenhagen, Lisbon, Oslo, Bucharest, Belgrade, Bern, Zagreb, Valletta, Dublin, Riga, Bratislava, Tallinn, Vilnius, Sofia, Chisinau, Podgorica, Minsk, Sarajevo, Tirana, Ljubljana, Reykjavik, Skopje.

This rating consists of elements, such as a score based on the features of the natural and geographical

location, the historical prerequisites for their formation, the number of tourist attraction objects (historical and cultural potential), the number of tourists infrastructure objects, as well as considering the factors of tourism development.

The main internal (endogenous) factors include logistics, seasonality, promotion of private tourism business development, increasing consumer awareness and changing their demand, increasing the importance of mass media in advertising and tourist services promotion, providing the tourism sector with personnel, increasing the role of coordination of tourism activities and monopolization processes.

External (exogenous) factors are natural-geographical, social, demographic, integration (globalization), political-legal, technological, environmental and cultural-historical aspects. The score based on the features of the natural and geographical location was considering mainly the location of a particular capital on the sea coasts or rivers, and always acted as one of the significant factors of the survivability of a settlement at a given geographical point.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Characteristics of the object of study

The city is a complex multifunctional system. The functions of cities as tourism centers include general features, such as administrative-political, cultural, scientific, organizational, transport, industrial, trade and distribution, and financial.

Besides, they are characterized by exactly tourist and recreational functions, as well as some specific ones related directly to tourism, such as the presence of monumental architectural landmarks, the presence of the historical city center (in metropolitan cities), as well as the presentational attractiveness of the city.

At the same time, the level of development of the tourism industry in a certain territory is expressed through the provision level of tourism facilities, its territorial differentiation, the effectiveness of tourism enterprises, the economic role of tourism for a given territory (the amount of income and expenses for tourism, the tourist balance; the place of tourism among other economic sectors).

Figure 1. The efficiency of forming the resources of an urban tourist destination.

Source: own elaboration.

In a city that is attractive from a tourist viewpoint, the efficiency of forming the resources of a tourist destination, including commercial, budgetary, and social efficiency, is important for tourist demand (Figure 1).

We believe that these factors are crucial for the existence of tourist demand, but they are also reinforced by another important factor – the image of the city, that is, its image in the imagination of the visitor. This factor can be stimulating if the image of the city has a positive character, or limiting if it is negative (for example, expensiveness or significant danger). Thus, the city should have a generalized image – the totality of all its characteristics in the imagination of a person.

In each city, tourist resources can be divided into four groups by type: cultural and historical, sacred, sightseeing, and educational and entertaining. In turn, these four types of tourist resources include: culture, traditions, history, sights, art, architectural ensembles, urban landscapes, convenient transport links, a large selection of accommodation and catering facilities, availability of various types of services, safety, the ability to communicate with a large number of people and etc.

Thus, the resource factor determines the totality of the tourist and recreational potential of a city and is one of the main criteria when choosing a city for tourists.

4.2 Results

Having analyzed the various components of the tourist potential of European capitals, we compiled a cumulative rating of these cities as tourism centers. This rating is compiled based on the total tourist and recreational potential of each of the European capitals because it characterizes the cities as capitals and their cultural and historical significance.

According to our rating of the capitals of Europe based on the number of tourist destinations, the top ten cities of tourist and recreational potential included (by the degree of reduction) Rome, Berlin, Athens, Madrid, Amsterdam, and Budapest. Five cities, such as Kishinev, Reykjavik, Skopje, Tirana, and Podgorica, are at the end of this rating since they have the lowest number of points (five each) and, accordingly, the smallest number of objects illustrating their historical and cultural potential.

But among them, one can single out the leader in the number of monuments of architecture, history, archeology, and monumental art, which is Reykjavik (482 monuments) and the capital with the smallest number of such monuments – Podgorica (337 monuments).

According to the rating of European capitals in terms of the number of tourist industry facilities, the leaders in terms of the number of main tourist infrastructure facilities are Paris, London, and Rome (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Rating of the European capitals in terms of the number of tourist destinations.

Source: Compiled by the authors.

The factor of transport communication is developed at a high level, especially in the capitals of Western and Central Europe.

Since the largest capitals of Europe lie on the main axes of the world settlement framework, they are

respectively transport hubs of regional and global importance. At the same time, having analyzed the various components of the tourist potential of the capital cities of Europe, it is possible to derive a cumulative rating of these cities as international tourism centers (Figure 3).

Figure 3 shows the top 10 positions that scored high in the aggregate rating.

Figure 3. Ranking of European capitals by total tourist potential.

Source: Compiled by the authors.

Sarajevo, Tirana, Ljubljana, Reykjavik, and Skopje have received the lowest score, ranging from 27 to 18. But this does not mean that these cities have a weak tourist potential and lack prospects for further development of tourism. This fact just means that tourism for these cities is not a priority at the moment, or is still in the process of becoming. The rest of the capital cities of the Balkan Peninsula, the Baltic States, as well as Eastern Europe are in the second half of the rating and have contradictory aspects in the development of tourism or its unbalanced development.

According to the rating of the European capitals, in terms of the number of tourist industry objects and main tourist infrastructure objects, Paris, London, and Rome are the leaders, which scored 63, 51, and 45 points, respectively. They are followed by Berlin (43 points), Moscow (39), Madrid (38), Prague and Amsterdam (33), and Vienna (31).

The rating is completed by Sarajevo (11 points), Minsk (10), Reykjavik (9), as well as Skopje and Tirana (8). The development level of tourist infrastructure in these cities, except for Reykjavik, is still at an insufficient level, although there is a tendency to increase capacity in the tourism sector. In general, the capital cities of Europe have a high infrastructural potential and are well provided with

tourist and infrastructure resources, namely accommodation, catering, and leisure facilities.

The transport network is developed at a high level, especially in the capitals of Western and Central Europe. As for the destinations of tourist flows, the main ones are directed to such cities as Berlin, Paris, London, Amsterdam, Moscow, Madrid, Rome, Athens, Prague, and Budapest. A greater number of other European capitals are covered by secondary destinations of tourist flows.

Besides, due to the large tourist attraction of the European region, it is characterized by a significant flow of international tourists visiting Europe (Lapointe et al., 2018). The most popular tourist destinations in this region are European capitals. They concentrate a significant part of the tourist and recreational potential, which distinguishes them from other European cities.

4.3 Discussion

The results of our approach to assessing the development of urban destinations are consistent with the works of Adashova (2019), Vishnevskaya (2020), Evsyukov (2019), Koroleva (2019), Molchanova (2020), and Petrenko (2020).

The reliability of the presented approaches is confirmed by the fact that most of the studied cities have medium and high indicators of total tourist and recreational potential (Park et al., 2020). Only some of the capital cities of the Balkan Peninsula, the Baltic States, and Eastern Europe have a rather low tourist and recreational potential, mainly because there is still a rather insignificant infrastructure provision of tourism in quantitative terms (Rodríguez et al., 2020).

The tourist flow directions, as well as their capacity, are qualitative characteristics that deepen this socio-geographical research in the field of tourism (Gkoumas, 2019; Baksi, Parida, 2020). According to our results, the attendance rate is of great importance for characterizing the development of tourism in a particular territory. It expresses the relative level of popularity of this tourist destination among tourists, holiday-makers, and visitors, which also largely applies to cities (Zheng et al., 2021).

A more powerful tourist flow to a particular city indicates its attractiveness as a territory for recreation and entertainment. The main factors that can stimulate (or limit) the tourist flow to any city in the country are, first of all, the level of its tourist resource base (in this case, it is more appropriate to talk about cultural and historical tourist and recreational resources), service level and quality, as well as the security and the price factor. An important role in forming tourist flows to the city is also played by its popularity and image.

5 CONCLUSION

Summing up, it can be noted that the city as a tourist destination is a settlement that has a sufficient number of tourist and recreational resources, social infrastructure facilities, at least one type of transport accessibility, and positions itself as a tourist center within the state to which it belongs. At the same time, internal and external factors have a significant impact on tourism development in cities.

Measures, aimed at developing the tourist and recreational sector in tourist cities should provide for comprehensive solutions to priority problems of the development of cities and their main tourist zones, further strengthening of tourist-excursion and sanatorium-resort services, expanding the range of recreational and tourist services, and creating an appropriate material, technical and personnel base, increasing the volume of income from tourist activities of all types.

The increase in tourist flows to urban tourist destinations will be facilitated by implementing geomarketing programs to promote them on the international tourist market, which will receive material and legal support from the state, as well as by creating foreign representative offices for tourist organizations that would be engaged in positioning cities in different countries worldwide.

REFERENCES

- Adashova, T. A., & Rogoten, N. N. (2019). Transformation of urban space as a factor in the development of the economy of impressions. *Modern Problems of Service and Tourism*, 13(2), 34-41.
- Agamirova, Ek. V., Agamirova, El. V., Lebedeva, O. Ye., Lebedev, K. A., & Ilkevich, S. V. (2017). Methodology of estimation of quality of tourist product. *Quality - Access to Success*, 18(157), 82-84.
- Baksi, A. K., & Parida, B. B. (2020). Exploring Relationship Between Controllable Metrics and Socio-Environmental Performance Indicators in Responsible Tourism Context Using Temporal Causal Model. *Anais Brasileiros De Estudos Turísticos*, 10(1, 2 e 3). <https://doi.org/10.34019/2238-2925.2020.v10.29960>
- Choi, Y., Hickerson, B., Lee, J., Lee, H., Choe, Y. (2022). Digital Tourism and Wellbeing: Conceptual Framework to Examine Technology Effects of Online Travel Media. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19095639>
- Chu, Q.; Bao, G.; Sun, J. (2022). Progress and Prospects of Destination Image Research in the Last Decade. *Sustainability*, 14, 10716. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141710716>

- Evsyukov, M. V., & Gomilevskaya, G. A. (2019). Classification of walking tours in urban tourist destinations. *Scientific, Technical and Economic Cooperation of the APR Countries in the 21st century*, 2, 267-270.
- Gkoumas A. (2019). Evaluating a standard for sustainable tourism through the lenses of local industry. *Heliyon*, 5(11), e02707. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e02707>
- Koroleva, O. V. (2019). Image messages and identity of a tourist destination: Promises of cities and expectations of tourists. *Urgent Problems of Humanities and Socio-Economic Sciences*, 13(6), 79-83.
- Ksenofontova, T. Y., Tarkhanova, N. P., Kosheleva, T. N., Voronov, A. A., & Luchaninov, R. S. (2021). Leading directions of tourism development in ural region. *Journal of Environmental Management and Tourism*, 12(8), 2038–2045. [https://doi.org/10.14505/jemt.v12.8\(56\).02](https://doi.org/10.14505/jemt.v12.8(56).02)
- Lapointe, D., Sarrasin, B., & Benjamin, C. (2018). Tourism in the Sustained Hegemonic Neoliberal Order. *Latin American Journal of Tourismology*, 4(1), 16–33. <https://doi.org/10.34019/2448-198X.2018.v4.13915>
- Lee, C.W., Li, C. (2019). The Process of Constructing a Health Tourism Destination Index. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(22). <https://doi.org/10.3390%2Fijerph16224579>
- Lukiyanchuk, I. N., Panasenko, S. V., Kazantseva, S. Yu., Lebedev, K. A., & Lebedeva, O. E. (2020). Development of online retailing logistics flows in a globalized digital economy. *Revista Inclusiones*, 7(S2-1), 407-416.
- Markova, O. V., Listopad, E. Ye., Shelygov, A. V., Fedorov, A. G., & Kiselevich, I. V. (2021). Economic and legal aspects of the innovative activity of enterprises in the context of the digital economy. *Nexo Revista Cientifica*, 34(2), 964-972. <https://doi.org/10.5377/nexo.v34i02.11623>
- Molchanova, V. A. (2020). New research models and public participation in developing innovative strategies of tourist destinations. *Humanitarian Scientific Bulletin*, 6, 54-58.
- Ogloblina, E. V., Seredina, M. I., Altunina, J. O., Kodolov, V. A., & Lebedev, K. A. (2020). Socio-economic consequences of digital development of the economy. *Revista Inclusiones*, 7(S3-5), 421-430.
- Park, S., Xu, Y., Jiang, L., Chen, Z., & Huang, S. (2020). Spatial structures of tourism destinations: A trajectory data mining approach leveraging mobile big data. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2020.102973>
- Petrenko, N. E. (2020). The role and importance of urban tourism in the contemporary regional agenda. *Bulletin of the Belgorod University of Cooperation, Economics, and Law*, 6(85), 181-188.
- Rodríguez, C., Jacob, M., & Florido, C. (2020). Socioeconomic Profile of Tourists with a Greater Circular Attitude and Behaviour in Hotels of a Sun and Beach Destination. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(24), 9392. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17249392>
- Santangelo, J. S., Rivkin, L. R., & Johnson, M. (2018). The evolution of city life. *Proceedings. Biological sciences*, 285(1884), 20181529. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2018.1529>
- Samadi Parviznejad, P., & Akhavan, A. N. (2021). Impact of the Tourism Industry Scenarios in Urban Economy: (Case Study Tabriz). *International Journal of Innovation in Management, Economics and Social Sciences*, 1(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.52547/ijimes.1.1.1>
- Solomina, I. Yu. (2016). Tourist space of the city: concept and specifics. In: Culture and tourism as tools for increasing the human potential of the nation: Proceedings of the All-Russian Scientific and Practical Conference, St. Petersburg, April 14–15, 2016 (pp. 368-374). St. Petersburg: D.A.R.K Publishing House.
- Vishnevskaya, E. V. (2020). Analysis of demand for the sights of the city of Belgorod based on search queries. *Scientific Result. Business and Service Technologies*, 6(2), 20-31.
- Yang, Zh., Zhang, Sh., Liu, J., Sun, H. (2022). Network of Tourism–Industrial Complex in Cities: Typologies and Implications through a Critical Literature Review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(9). <https://doi.org/10.3390%2Fijerph19094934>
- Zavalko, N. A., Kozhina, V. O., Zhakevich, A. G., Matyunina, O. E., & Lebedeva, O. Ye. (2017). Methodical approaches to rating the quality of financial control at the enterprise. *Quality - Access to Success*, 18(161), 69-72.
- Zheng, M. Y., Chen, C. C., Lin, H. H., Tseng, C. H., & Hsu, C. H. (2021). Research on the impact of popular tourism program involvement on rural tourism image, familiarity, motivation and willingness. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13094906>

Table 1. CRediT author statement

Term	Definition	Author 1	A.2	A.3	A.4	A.5
Conceptualization	Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims	+	+	+		
Methodology	Development or design of methodology; creation of models			+	+	+
Software	Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components				+	
Validation	Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/ reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs	+	+	+		+
Formal analysis	Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyze or synthesize study data			+	+	
Investigation	Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection	+				+
Resources	Provision of study materials, reagents, materials, patients, laboratory samples, animals, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools			+	+	+

Term	Definition	Author 1	A.2	A.3	A.4	A.5
Data Curation	Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later reuse	+	+			+
Writing – Original Draft	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation)	+		+	+	+
Writing - Review & Editing	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre-or post-publication stages		+		+	
Visualization	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/ data presentation	+		+		+
Supervision	Oversight and leadership responsibility for the research activity planning and execution, including mentorship external to the core team	+	+		+	
Project administration	Management and coordination responsibility for the research activity planning and execution			+		+
Funding acquisition	Acquisition of the financial support for the project leading to this publication	+	+	+	+	+

Source: adapted from Elsevier (2022, s/p), based upon Brand et al. (2015).

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